

INDICATORS IN TITRATIONS WITH CERIC SULPHATE

By T. K. S. MURTHY AND Bh. S. V. RAGHAVA RAO

Crystal violet, a commercial dye, has been shown to be suitable in titrations with ceric sulphate. Its range of usefulness is great compared with other indicators. Comparative studies on other indicators, viz., Xylene cyanol FF, *N*-phenylanthranilic acid and Rhodamine 6G are reported, extending their use to titration other than those originally recommended.

In spite of the excellence of ceric sulphate as a reagent in oxidimetry, its use has not become widespread through absence of suitable and readily available indicators. Willard and Young (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 3260) employed *ortho*-phenanthroline-ferrous complex with great success in a variety of reactions with this reagent, but its use is largely handicapped by its scarcity. Other indicators with a limited application have been reported by various investigators, chief amongst which may be mentioned the following. Xylene cyanol FF by Mitchell and Ward ("Modern Methods in Quantitative Chemical Analysis", 1932); *N*-phenylanthranilic acid by Suerokomoski and Stepin (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 9287). More recently one of us (*Curr. Sci.*, 1947, 16, 378) reported the use of Rhodamine 6G and its application appears to be more extensive than originally reported. During an extended series of investigations on suitable indicators we have noticed that Crystal violet, a commercial dye, possesses a range of usefulness far greater than any indicator we know of, with the exception of ferrous-phenanthroline complex; besides, its colour change, green to orange-red, is not only easily detectable but very sharp. Our investigations have also disclosed that *N*-phenylanthranilic acid (*loc. cit.*) may be employed in the titration of a number of other substances (*vide infra*), particularly trivalent antimony, in the presence of iodine monochloride; in the latter case excellent results are obtained if the indicator is added towards the end of the titration.

We have further carried out comparative studies on some of these indicators. Table I summarises our results. The titration of either oxalic acid or arsenious acid has not been successful. Xylene cyanol FF has been found unsuitable except in the originally recommended titration of ferrous iron and the end-point is very sharp only if the acid content of the solution does not exceed 0.5*N*.

It has further been found that ferrous iron may be titrated accurately in the presence of oxalic acid by Xylene cyanol FF and Crystal violet, provided the acid concentration is not above 1.0*N* and sufficient quantity of phosphoric acid is added, as is evident from Table IIb. With the former indicator, however, colour change towards the end is slow. This last observation is in conformity with the findings of Ferri (*Quart. Jour. & Year-book Pharm.*, 1937, 10, 351).

TABLE I

Ceric sulphate = 0.05N. Total vol. = 100 c.c. Overall acidity = 0.8N in HCl or H_2SO_4 . Indicator = 3-4 drops of 0.1% aqueous solution of crystal violet.

Amount taken.	* Amount found with		
	Crystal violet.	Rhodamine 6G.	Phenylanthranilic acid.
1. Ferrous ammonium sulphate.			
0.1203 g.	0.1203 g.	0.1203 g.	0.1203 g.
0.1928	0.1928	0.1928 g	0.1928
0.3855	0.3855	0.3855	0.3855
0.7710	0.7710	0.7710	0.7710
2. Ferric chloride after reduction with $SnCl_2$.			
0.1123 g.	0.1124 g.		0.1124 g.
0.1235	0.1236	Not suitable.	0.1237
0.2470	0.2470		0.2470
3. Hydrogen peroxide.			
0.00783 g.	0.00783 g.	0.00783 g.	0.00783 g.
0.0162	0.0162	0.0162	0.0162
0.0324	0.0324	0.0324	0.0324
4. Uranyl acetate after reduction with Zn and HCl.			
		(a)	(a)
0.1106 g.	0.1202 g.	0.1200 g.	0.1200 g.
0.1622	0.1622	0.1622	0.1622
0.2392	0.2396	0.2400	0.2400
5. Potassium ferrocyanide.			
			(a)
0.0412 g.	0.0412 g.	0.0412 g.	0.0412 g.
0.1000	0.1002	0.1005	0.1005
0.2000	0.2002	0.2000	0.2002
6. Hydroquinone.			
		(a)	
0.0146 g.	0.0146 g.	0.0146 g.	0.0146 g.
0.0151	0.0151	0.0151	0.0151
0.0302	0.0302	0.0302	0.0302
7. Stannous chloride.			
			(a)
0.0561 g.	0.0560 g.	0.0561 g.	0.0560 g.
0.0605	0.0608	0.0605	0.0603
0.1210	0.1210	0.1212	0.1212
8. Antimony (trivalent). (Sb_2O_3).			
(5 c.c. of 0.005M-ICI added and titrated at 50°).			
			(a)
0.0190 g.			0.0191 g.
0.0205	Unsuitable.	Unsuitable.	0.0205
0.0410			0.0422

The indicator is added towards the end.

* Each figure represents an average of four titrations

(a) Signifies the indicator has been employed for the first time in this titration.

TABLE IIA

Titration of Mohr's salt in presence of oxalic acid.

Ferrous ammonium sulphate taken = 0.3885M. Indicator = Crystal violet. Total volume = 100 c.c.

Overall acidity.	Oxalic acid added.	Mohr's salt found.	Remarks.
0.5N	0.0252 g.	0.04008 g.	The reaction is slow towards the end.
"	0.0504	0.075	
"	0.0756	0.1075	
"	0.1080	0.1480	
"	0.1260	0.4090	
"	0.1512	0.4090	
1.0	0.0252	0.4180	End-point is sharp. Titration not successful.
2.0	0.0252	—	

TABLE IIB

Titration of Mohr's salt in the presence of oxalic acid on addition of phosphoric acid.

Total vol. of the soln. = 100 c.c. Syrupy phosphoric acid (d 1.8) added = 5 c.c.

Amount of Mohr's salt taken.	Overall acid concn. in HCl.	Amount of oxalic acid added.	Mohr's salt found with			
			Crystal violet.	Rhod-6G.	Phenyl-anthranilic acid.	Xylene cyanol FF.
0.1406 g.	0.8N	0.053 g.	0.1406 g.	0.1427 g.	0.1417 g.	0.1406 g.
"	2.0	0.053	0.1427	0.1427	0.1427	0.1427
0.3855	0.5	0.13	0.3855	0.3887	0.3887	0.3856
"	1.0	0.13	0.3855	0.3920	0.3887	The end-point is not detectable.
"	"	0.26	0.3855	0.3920	0.3902	
"	"	0.32	0.3855	0.3920	0.3902	
0.7710	1.0	0.32	0.7710	0.7780	0.7760	
"	"	0.64	0.7710	0.7780	0.7760	
"	"	1.28	0.7710	0.7769	0.7769	

Besides, it appears to be a prerequisite in practically all titrations with ceric sulphate, employing reversible indicators, that the strength of the titrant is not higher than 0.05N, and the overall acidity with respect to hydrochloric acid or sulphuric acid lies between 1N and 2N. Further, in many cases a large excess of the titrant oxidises the indicator irreversibly or at any rate, its sensitiveness largely impaired.